
MEDICINAL BIOMAGNETISM – PRESENTATION OF PROTOCOL FOR PSORIASIS TREATMENT

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ABSTRACT

Medicinal Biomagnetism (MB) is an integrative and complementary therapeutic system that is non-invasive, painless, and low-cost. It uses medium-intensity magnets to restore the pH balance of cell structures by means of depolarizing Biomagnetic Pairs (BMP). Psoriasis is an example of a condition for which MB may be used as an adjunctive treatment. It is a chronic, autoimmune, and recurrent inflammatory skin disease that affects both men and women of any age. It affects between 2 and 3% of the world's population and is difficult to treat. Through a qualitative, narrative, and exploratory literature review, the aim is to present the theory of Biomagnetic Pair or Medicinal Biomagnetism, as well as its physical diagnostic examination technique, called Complete Scanning, and the specific protocols associated with the treatment of Psoriasis. We present an

alternative for complementary treatment of this disease using MB, as well as a suggestion for its application in controlled clinical trials.

Keywords: Medicinal Biomagnetism; Biomagnetic Pair; Protocol; Psoriasis; Integrative and Complementary Therapies; Static Magnetic Field; Magnets.

1 INTRODUCTION

The modern world has been dealing with new chronic and autoimmune diseases consisting in the immune system's attack on the body's own cells. Antibodies that serve to protect against health antigens by the defense system may easily confuse and attack healthy cells (O'BRYAN, 2018). According to Myers (2016), "when conventional doctors have to treat autoimmune disorders, they offer to 'manage' the problem instead of 'solving' it. The reason is simple: they do not believe that autoimmune disorders may be cured."

An important autoimmune disease to study is psoriasis. On May 24, 2014, the World Health Organization (WHO) approved a historic resolution to combat the stigma suffered by people with psoriasis. All Member States recognized the burden of psoriasis and committed to increasing their efforts to combat the stigma and unnecessary exclusion of people living with psoriasis. In addition to being classified as a severe non-communicable disease, the distress related to misdiagnosis, inadequate treatment, and stigmatization of the disease was highlighted, and the preparation of a global report on psoriasis was determined, carried out in 2015 and published in 2016, under the title "Global report on psoriasis" (WHO, 2016).

The report found that psoriasis is not a disease that only affects adults and may occur at any age. Studies identified the age of 33 as the average age of onset of the disease, and 75% of cases occurred before the age of 46 (NEVITT and HUTCHINSON, 1996). In addition to the skin and nail involvement (NATARAJAN et al., 2010), psoriasis may be associated with an inflammatory arthritis known as psoriatic arthritis (SMITH et al., 2016), which involves the spine and joints. People diagnosed with psoriasis have a higher risk of developing cardiovascular disease (ABUABARA et al., 2010; HU and LAN, 2017). According to Jameson and

colleagues (2020), “patients with psoriasis had a higher risk of metabolic syndrome, morbidity, and mortality from cardiovascular events.” In addition, psoriasis affects mental health because people with this disease have significant social stigma (WHO, 2016).

The role of the immune system in the cause of psoriasis has been the subject of important research. The etiology of psoriasis cannot be confirmed with certainty, although there is evidence of genetic predisposition (HARDEN et al., 2015; WOLFF et al., 2019). “The etiology of psoriasis is still not well understood, but there is an unequivocal genetic component” (VENTURA et al., 2017). According to Harden and colleagues (2015), “Psoriasis is a chronic, non-communicable, painful, disfiguring, and disabling disease for which there is no cure; it has a significant negative impact on the quality of life of those who suffer from this disease.”

The WHO reports that various triggering factors lead to the first manifestation of psoriasis, including body weight, alcohol, and smoking (DANIELSEN et al., 2017). Certain infections such as streptococcal throat infection are an important aggravating or initiating factor for the disease (DE JESÚS-GIL et al., 2018). Periodontitis has also been associated with an increased risk of psoriasis (SKUDUTYTE-RYSSTAD et al., 2014). Understanding and minimizing these triggers may assist in the treatment of psoriasis (WHO, 2016).

In addition to painful and debilitating physical symptoms, the psychological and mental health of patients with this disease is severely compromised, including low self-esteem, sexual dysfunction, anxiety, depression, and suicidal ideation (RUSSO et al., 2004). It impairs the lives of patients when psoriasis is present in visible areas of the skin, such as the face and hands (MEROLA et al., 2018).

The prevalence of psoriasis in different countries varies between 0.09% and 11.43%, making psoriasis a serious global problem affecting approximately 100 million individuals worldwide (WHO, 2016). Recent data from the Brazilian Society of Dermatology estimate the prevalence of psoriasis in Brazil to be 1.31%, which results in approximately 3 million people with 73.4% of Brazilian patients with

moderate to severe psoriasis reporting compromised health-related quality of life (ROMITI et al., 2020).

According to the WHO Report (2016), health systems must adopt a paradigm shift in health services provided, financed, managed, and delivered to the population. They must focus on people and respond to their needs and preferences. People must participate in their own care and be supported to do so. Health systems must be reliable and respond to people's needs and preferences in a humane and holistic manner (WHO, 2016).

This research is justified for contribute to minimizing the suffering and physical, psychological, and social effects caused by the autoimmune disease psoriasis to those who struggle to get rid of or at least mitigate its harmful effects. Furthermore, it is important to collaborate in meeting one of the recommendations of the WHO, which defines person-centered holistic healthcare services as the ideal treatment model for psoriasis. This is undeniably one of the fundamental principles of Medicinal Biomagnetism (MB).

1.1 STATIC MAGNETIC FIELDS

In the second half of the 20th century with the technological advancements achieved it was possible to conduct scientific studies proving the effects of magnetic fields on animals, plants, and cells. Biomagnetism was validated as part of an evolving scientific doctrine. It is now known that the magnetic field is the cause and bioelectricity is its effect. Metabolism causes local pH imbalance, turning us into a living battery. Thus, the discharge of this battery through bioelectric currents is called life. In this sense, biomagnetism is a fundamental tool that acts on the essence of life (DE LA CAL, 2004).

According to Carneiro and colleagues (2000), the ionic currents flow due to the depolarization of cells (brain, heart, nerves) in paramagnetic substances (liver), ferromagnetic substances (lung), and magnetic markers present in the body, which originate magnetic fields in biological systems.

As Broeringmeyer (1991) explains, due to the different chemical activities of the body, different organs produce fluctuating magnetic fields. Each cell has a specific magnetic value. This has resulted in the theory that we are electromagnetic entities and that our bodies are made up of electromagnetic energy fields.

In the work carried out by Marycz and colleagues (2018) on the magnetic influence of electric currents and magnetic materials on living and inanimate matter, cells were able to communicate by sending and receiving electromagnetic signals (magnetic resonance). Thus, the application of Static Magnetic Fields (SMF) and their possible effects on the fate of stem cells represent an interesting perspective in the field of tissue engineering, in which these cells are applied to regenerate damaged tissues and organs.

Krueger-Beck and colleagues (2010), in a study entitled “Electric and Magnetic Fields (EMF) applied to peripheral nerve regeneration” concluded that the application of EMF in animal tissue is related to axonal elongation and orientation, protein increase, genetic alteration, and reduction of total regeneration time. The applied EMF does not produce physical damage and presents few transient side effects when used at magnitudes considered safe.

It is evident that the development of life is linked to magnetic radiation and plants, humans, and animals are affected by this phenomenon. Therefore, it is of paramount importance to understand in-depth how the magnetic and electromagnetic field influences living beings. Furthermore, discovering how to manipulate and obtain benefits from their properties, either for direct application or for the development of systems and equipment has the potential to improve the quality of life and health (Salinas and Silva, 2012).

Medicinal Biomagnetism (MB) is one of these systems that still require further studies to prove its clinical results.

1.2 MEDICINAL BIOMAGNETISM (MB)

It is important to distinguish Biomagnetism from MB. The former is the study of magnetic fields generated by living organisms with the aim of identifying biophysical information for clinical diagnosis and therapy of pathologies (CARNEIRO et al., 2000). The latter is a technique developed in the 1980 by the Mexican physiotherapist Isaac Goiz Durán (DURÁN, 1994).

MB applied to health may be understood as a non-invasive complementary integrative therapy system. Its technique uses static magnetic fields generated by medium intensity therapeutic magnets applied externally to the body on the Biomagnetic Pairs (BMP) (DURÁN, 2008). A BMP may harbor pathogenic microorganisms (DURÁN, 2008; FRANK, 2017), free radicals, endogenous toxins, which are the cause of many health problems such as pain, inflammation, infections, among others (VALKO et al., 2006; DURÁN, 2008). The dysfunction polarizes charges of biochemical elements hindering the physiological neutralization that naturally occurs between acidic and basic substances in the body; it makes difficult for organic systems such as the immune, nervous, lymphatic and excretory systems to communicate with each other (DURÁN, 1996).

The application of MB restores the body's ability to eliminate pathogenic agents such as viruses, fungi, bacteria and parasites, as well as stimulate self-correction of glandular dysfunctions and promote detoxification through natural pathways of the body. It treats individuals as a whole and corrects the energetic cause of their illnesses, taking into account their biological individuality (DURÁN, 2008).

In the therapeutic process, the Biomagnetism Therapist focuses on finding BMP through a physical diagnosis exam of these pairs, also called scanning. The physical exam seeks an autonomous, kinesiological response, studied by Henrique de Juan González de Castejón in his Doctoral thesis in Medicine at the University of Alcalá (2015). The kinesiological response refers to bioelectromagnetic dysfunctions and was named the "Goiz Reflex" in honor of the technique's developer (BROERINGMEYER, 1991).

The aim of MB is to depolarize BMP, stimulating the regulation of the organism's bioelectric balance through the impact of magnets on the charges of dysfunction that resonate with each other. This leads to the adjustment of the region pH encompassed by the field, bringing the organism to homeostasis (DURÁN, 2008).

Using the BMP scanning, Durán (1996) observed the shortening of the right hemibody after application of a static magnetic field of north-polarity (negative) on the thymus. It generated an accumulation of negative charges causing a reflex contraction of the right hemibody. Visually, the observed mechanical effect consisted in a misalignment of the patient's heels that was lying in a dorsal position (shortening of the right leg). Following this, Durán deduced that the hemibody would align if it was possible to find the point of accumulation of resonant positive charges. This was achieved when he applied a south-polarity (positive) magnet near the coccyx bone of his patient which later it was identified as the rectum, resulting in the realignment of the lower limbs. Durán called these two organic dysfunctional points the Thymus/Rectum Pair, demonstrated in (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Thymus/Rectum Biomagnetic Pair

The upper image demonstrates the excess of the free radical OH⁻ (increase in alkalinity – north pole of the BMP) in the thymus region. The lower image shows the excess of the H⁺ (increase in acidity – south pole of the BMP) in the rectum region. These points are in magnetic resonance, called “THYMUS/RECTUM” BMP. To treat the bioelectromagnetic dysfunction, the north pole (black) of the magnet should be applied to the excess of OH⁻ and the south pole (red) of another magnet to the excess of H⁺ charges. Source: Bossa (2021a; 2021b; 2021c).

After identifying the Thymus/Rectum Pair, Durán continued to identify new pairs that supported other dysfunctions, from infectious microorganisms to pairs modulating physiological activity. This led to the systematization of a map for scanning the whole organism called “Complete Scanning” (CS).

According to Durán (2008), health depends on tissue and cellular pH which should remain close to neutral values and may be detected and adjusted through magnetic fields produced by medium-intensity magnets. Rebalancing the pH through depolarization with magnets allows for the free flow of energy restoring health to living organisms.

As mentioned earlier, the gold standard treatment of MB is complete scanning which treats each organism individually. To enhance the medium- and long-term effects of scanning, specific protocols were developed for certain types of pathologies. These protocols were developed based on the results obtained from complete scanning of several complaints and symptoms, both reported by patients and diagnosed by medical teams and specific tests. The most repeated BMP during the treatment of a particular complaint were computed and grouped to form MB protocols (MARTÍNEZ, 2017a and; 2017b and; BOSSA, 2021b). Among them there is the Protocol for autoimmune diseases (systemic lupus erythematosus, psoriasis, rheumatoid arthritis, multiple sclerosis) (MARTÍNEZ, 2017b). The protocol was designed to complement the practice of MB. These protocols are not more important than the CS but serve to impact prophylactically, if necessary, enhancing the effect of complete scanning (MARTÍNEZ, 2017b; BOSSA, 2021b).

For the adjunctive treatment of psoriasis using MB we present the Basic Protocol (BP) (Figure 2), the SIS Immunological Protocol (Figure 3), and the SIS Dermatological Protocol (Figure 4)

It is important to apply the negative magnet to the anatomical point, checking for any imbalance in the length of the right leg and applying the positive magnet to the corresponding resonance location (MARTÍNEZ, 2018). The BMP main function is detoxification, optimization of immune activity, modulation of the sympathetic, parasympathetic, and endocrine nervous systems (MARTÍNEZ, 2017a and; 2017b and; BOSSA, 2021b).

Figure 2: Basic Protocol

1. Liver-Liver
2. Liver-Kidney (D)
3. Kidney (D/E) - Kidney (D / E)
4. Medulla Oblongata-Lumbar 3/4
5. Supraspinatus (D/ E) - Supraspinatus (D / E)
6. Thymus-Reto
7. Hip (D / E) - Hip (D / E)
8. Cardia-Appendix
9. Transverse Colon-Liver
10. Thyroid (D/ E) - thyroid (CL)
11. Vagina (D/E) - Vagina (CL) (testicles)
12. Lumbar-Kidney (D / E)

Lumbar 3 / Lumbar 4. Source: Bossa (2021b), adapted from Martínez (2017a e; 2017b).

The SIS immune protocol potentiates normal immune activity. The aim is to treat dysfunctions generated by recurrent inflammation which leads to the worsening

of signs, symptoms, and the chronicity of the condition; it is basic characteristics of an autoimmune disease (MARTÍNEZ, 2017a and; 2017b; BOSSA, 2021b).

Figure 3: SIS immune (Autoimmune diseases)

D/E: Right/Left; CL: Contralateral. Source: Bossa (2021b), adapted from Martínez (2017a e; 2017b).

Finally, the SIS Dermatological assists in all processes related to the skin and its associated to microbiota, such as pruritus, erythema, bleeding, itching, scaling, and burning (MARTÍNEZ, 2017a and; 2017b; BOSSA, 2021b).

Figure 4: SIS Dermatological

D/E: Right/Left; CL: Contralateral; C: Central. Source: Bossa (2021b), adapted from Martínez (2017a e; 2017b).

Thus, in line with the guidelines proposed by the WHO which suggests a holistic approach to the treatment of autoimmune disease psoriasis, the present study is an integrative therapeutic option available to patients with the disease in focus on CS and MB complementary protocols.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The methodology employed in the preparation of this article consisted of qualitative bibliographic research. This study aimed to investigate a previously established hypothesis before starting the analytical work; it means that the researcher must adopt an attitude of respect, objectivity, and impartiality (GIL, 2008). The study consisted of gathering knowledge about the subject through the search, reading, and comparison of different bibliographic materials, synthesizing the approach of various authors.

The type of research carried out in this work was narrative research using narratives as a method and as a phenomenon of study (PINNEGAR and DAYNES, 2007). This research is exploratory in maintaining a greater understanding of the problem, as well as to develop ideas with a view to formulating research problems and hypotheses for subsequent studies (GIL, 2008).

The search for articles was conducted between 2010 and 2022 using the electronic databases PubMed, SciELO, and Google Scholar. Full-text articles in English, Spanish, and Portuguese were included with priority given to articles presenting a Digital Object Identifier (DOI). The choice of databases was based on their accessibility and reliability. The search terms used to locate the articles are described in Table 1.

Inclusion criteria of articles was based on their relevance to the field of the present study. Articles whose content did not meet the criteria defined for the research or were outside the scope of the selected languages were excluded.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

According to the search terms chosen for the electronic database searches, 149 publications were selected. Of these references, seven were related to MB with two articles having DOI and four books being cited, while the other eight were discarded for not being related to the research theme. In this case, considering the need to present the technique of MB and the protocols, books and course materials were included totaling 17 references. Regarding Psoriasis, 20 publications with DOI related to the research object were found. In addition, publications of relevance and citations from books were included, totaling 24 references. Regarding the Static Magnetic Fields theme, four articles with DOI and citations from books related to the topic were selected, totaling six references.

Table 1: Results from literature search

Research terms	Platform	Filters	Articles searched	Articles selected	Articles excluded
psoriasis, streptococcus infection, throat throat	PubMed	2010-2022, full-text	23	5	18
psoriasis pathogenesis cardiovascular comorbid therapy	PubMed	<i>Idem</i>	20	5	15
psoriasis, genitals, hands, feet, nails,	PubMed	<i>Idem</i>	1	1	0
psoríase, nails, fungus	PubMed	<i>Idem</i>	6	2	4

psoriasis psoriatic, arthritis plaqueta-type	PubMed	<i>Idem</i>	14	1	13
algorithm brazilian consensus	PubMed	<i>Idem</i>	14	1	13
psorise autoimune	Google Scholar	Book, partial visualization	35	4	31
Who psoriasis report	Google Scholar	–	1	1	0
campos magnéticos estáticos	SciElo	–	7	0	7
Vida, radiações magnéticas	Google Scholar	Books, Full visualization	19	1	18
Smf cell fate	PubMed	2010-2022	4	1	3
Biomagnetismo	SciElo	–	0	0	0
Biomagnetismo ferramenta fundamental	Google Scholar	2010-2022, Portuguese	2	1	1
Biomagnetismo medicinal	PubMed	–	1	0	0
Biomagnetic pair therapy	PubMed	–	2	2	0

Source: The authors.

Following analysis of the selected materials it may be observed that the formation of BMP occurs in the electronic layer of the atom. According to nuclear physics it corresponds to a radioactive isotope that participates in chemical reactions emitting radiation and obtaining information about its behavior. The distortion occurs at the electromagnetic level which is one of the forces that give it support, both externally and internally, in the cellular membrane wall that surrounds each cell in the organism. This fact causes the improvement of entropy in organic systems consuming a greater amount of energy in order to return to its initial state of low energy consumption or system homeostasis (DURÁN, 2008).

The sum of imbalances weakens the organism as a whole. In this context, immunity decreases. The multiplication of pathogenic microorganisms tends to be an aggravating factor. Thus, the multiplication in the affected areas throughout this process leads the organism from a state of health to a state of disease (DURÁN, 2008). Disease occurs due to the oscillatory imbalance of cells; states of health and disease are the result of variations in the involved electrical potentials (NAHAS, 2017).

According to Tortora and Derrickson (2017), while the controlled conditions of the body remain within their respective tolerable limits, cells function efficiently, homeostasis is maintained, and the body remains healthy. However, if one or more components lose the ability to contribute to homeostasis, the balance of body processes may be disturbed. If the homeostatic imbalance is moderate, a disorder or disease may occur; if it is severe it may result in death.

Tortora and Derrickson (2017) also emphasize the maintenance of indispensable cellular equilibrium in living organisms. Furthermore, they highlight the need for internal body control mechanisms to function properly. Failure of these mechanisms could be fatal. For Durán (2008), homeostasis, that is, the Normal Energy Level (NEL) of living organisms occurs at around 1000 Gauss, as shown in Figure 5.

The MB technique seeks to identify bioenergetic imbalances causing the loss of internal body homeostasis to correct these dysfunctions of acid/base neutralization, whose have electromagnetic nature. Correction is achieved through magnetic stimulation with magnets that generate magnetic fields of medium intensity and vary between 1000 and 7500 Gauss, for approximately 30 minutes (MARTÍNEZ, 2017a, 2017b; DURÁN, 2008).

Figure 5: Normal Energy Level (NEL)

The following describes the BMP related to psoriasis. These pairs should be tested and impacted on the body of the patient with psoriasis. If the response to kinesiological testing (shortening of the right hemi-body) is proven, Durán (2008) affirms that it is the “true psoriasis”, because when these pairs are found in the same CS they are associated pairs. In this case, the BMP harbor the *streptococcus* A. and G. sustaining the disease (ZANGRILLI et al., 2022; KANDA, 2021; DE JESÚS-GIL et al., 2018; RUIZ-ROMEU et al., 2018; ALEKSEYENKO et al., 2013, FERRAN et al., 2013).

Durán (1994) describes the BMP Coronary – Lung (Left) and Brachial (Right) – Brachial (Left) as being the bioelectromagnetic dysfunctions and pH alterations that provide the biological terrain supporting the presence of the *streptococcus*

A. For Durán (1994), if the Brachial (Right) – Brachial (Left) BMP is associated with the Bladder – Bladder BMP – which may sustain the presence of another bacteria, *Streptococcus G.* – these associated pairs provide conditions for the development of specific signs and symptoms of psoriasis.

Currently, several studies that relating the *streptococcus* bacteria with the autoimmune disease psoriasis have been conducted and published in internationally renowned journals. It has been proved the presence of these microorganisms enabling the development of more effective medications to combat, although they are not free of side effects (ZANGRILLI et al., 2022; KANDA, 2021; DE JESÚS-GIL et al., 2020; RUIZ-ROMEU et al., 2018). It is important to highlight that Durán had already identified the presence of the aforementioned microorganisms in BMP in psoriasis patients, a fact that led him to name it “true psoriasis” (DURÁN, 1994).

According to Durán and colleagues (2005), the beneficial influence of magnets on the body is unquestionable. The application of magnets promotes magnetic flow through tissues, including the induction of secondary currents. The shock of currents with magnetic waves promotes an increase in temperature, as a result of the impact of electrons on the body's cells. These impactions are very effective for reducing pain and swelling in the body in general. There is an accelerated movement of hemoglobin in the body while calcium and cholesterol are reduced. Deposits of materials that adhere to the sides of the interior of veins, causing high blood pressure, decrease and tend to fade away. There is a cleansing of the blood and a consequent increase in circulation. Heart activities are facilitated and pain disappears. The autonomous functions of the nerves are normalized and the internal organs recover their own function.

Durán and colleagues claim that the secretion of hormones is promoted. Furthermore, all diseases related to hormonal secretion deficiency are attacked and disappear. Blood and lymph circulation are activated; all nutrients are efficiently transported to every cell in the body aiding in overall metabolism. Magnetic flow promotes health and provides energy by eliminating disorders. It

may give stimuli to multiple bodily functions, such as the circulatory, nervous, respiratory, digestive, and urinary systems (DURÁN et al., 2005).

To corroborate the therapeutic effects of MB a case study on psoriasis by María Teresa Torreblanca Huerta is highlighted (DÚRAN et al., 2005). The case reports a 74-year-old male patient who had been experiencing skin problems for approximately two months with instructions to avoid sunlight and apply hydrocortisone. The patient presented with pale skin, lost 6 kg in 15 days, lacked appetite, experienced fatigue that kept him resting, had a dry cough, and had serosanguineous secretions on his skin. The patient improved after the first session; the second day was characterized by the interruption of lesion suppurating; his overall condition improved including the pain in his scapular region. Six sessions were conducted with the first four on consecutive days and the last two with a ten-day interval. During the last session, the patient was examined and the healed lesions were found to have no secretions, paleness, or any other signs, and the patient showed overall improvement.

4. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

In conclusion, the suggested protocols for co-adjuvant treatment of the autoimmune disease psoriasis were presented in this literature review. Considering that MB therapy is a low-cost, non-invasive, and easy-to-apply tool, it may be concluded that these protocols are safe to use and their results may be analyzed. It is important to perform CS in all sessions and supplement with the application of BMP in the immune system and the dermatological SIS only if necessary to impact them. This procedure is used to ensure that none of the important pairs related to psoriasis are not depolarized.

This work suggests that larger clinical studies need to be conducted using the MB technique to reach the ideal methodology to be applied in accordance with the presented pathogenicity. Additionally, it becomes necessary to test the best frequency of treatment application, duration of exposure to static magnetic fields, treatment duration, follow-up maintenance, and other parameters.

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